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“CHALK DUST AND THE CURRICULUM THAT NEVER SOLVES US”

The board is full again with white ghosts of numbers
stacked like quiet expectations, no one ever remembers
equations pressing against walls, solutions that seem to vanish forever
I heard too many sighs, but not a relief instead to wonder.

I write $x = ?$ as if the question were simple,
as if the room were not like a temple
one filled with variables with time not ample
no formula was designed to hold and solution crumples

Chalk dust settles on my fingers, fine as the doubt
in a student's lowered eyes—like a terrible fight
a powder of unfinished thoughts, like a room with dim light
answers swallowed and it vanish in our sight.

We move through lessons like rehearsed confessions:
solve, substitute, simplify—but no one gives the solutions
on how to simplify hunger, how to substitute fear,
how to solve the long division of us being unseen.

The curriculum marches on, neatly printed,
immune to interruption but still it looks tainted
when a mind falters, mistakes usually created
leaving a silent battle in school that grows undefeated.

They say mathematics is certain—but I have seen certainty crack
in the tremble of a hand holding a pencil within a track.

I have seen infinity from a distance like a it is a bird's flock
that seems what is taught and understood are vast learning of facts.

“Try again,” I whisper, though I know we are not just retrying problems—
we are retrying belief, retrying worth, serving as emblems

retrying the fragile variable, constants and theorems
that everyone here can still be solved and the success is claimed.

And still, the bell rings—which helps me in realizing
that time, the only constant thing considers the meaning
that we cannot rearrange and solely decide on something
without other's support and our careful understanding

They leave in fragments, carrying numbers that do not fit,
proofs that prove nothing but small facts in it
about who they are and how they would act in skit
a total satisfaction when answer show and makes the light lit

I erase the board slowly and I watch the chalk disappear
like answers we never reached that makes it unclear
the dust remains— in the lungs, in the spaces in the air
a quiet reminder that some equations were never meant to be solved and make it clear.

